

“Tibbiyotning zamonaviy muammolari va ularning innovatsion yechimlari”

ONLAYN ILMIY KONFERENSIYA

27.12.2025

RECONSTRUCTIVE PLASTIC SURGERY TREATMENT METHODS FOR HYPERTROPHIC AND KELOID SCARS

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Relevance of the topic. Hypertrophic scars and keloids represent an abnormal wound-healing condition that culminates in scar formation. These pathological scars reflect persistent inflammation and are histologically characterized by fibroblast proliferation, neovascularization, and collagen deposition. Clinically, hypertrophic scars differ in the extent to which tissue extends relative to the wound margins. Keloids typically develop over months in areas where scars are subjected to tension, including the chest and joints, and may continue to extend beyond the original wound edges. Keloid scars most commonly occur in individuals with darker skin phototypes (Fitzpatrick 3–4) and may develop even after minor skin injury. These lesions tend to persist for a long time, often for several years, and are mainly localized on the earlobes, shoulder girdle, and chest. Keloids are frequently accompanied by subjective symptoms such as pain and itching and tend to exhibit progressive growth beyond the site of the initial trauma.

Purpose of the study. To evaluate the effectiveness of reconstructive plastic surgery techniques in the treatment of hypertrophic and keloid scars.

Materials and methods. A total of 84 patients with hypertrophic scars were included in the study, with a mean age of 14.4 years. The cohort consisted of 60.8% males and 39.2% females. The earliest time point for initiating treatment was 1 year after scar formation. The mean age at which treatment was initiated was 14.5 years. Scars were less common in children aged 1–7 years due to closer parental supervision. In clinical practice, we frequently observed cases managed conservatively at home (commonly with goose fat). These patients were typically admitted later due to scar-related contractures of the face, chin, or periorbital region. The mean scar area was 207.19 cm² (range: 18.00–1063.50 cm²).

Most patients sought treatment due to scars resulting from burns (55.8%), trauma

(13.3%), or surgical procedures (20.8%). Interestingly, in 28.3% of cases, patients presented after a prolonged period of waiting without receiving proper medical care following the initial injury.

Based on the nature of the injury, all patients were classified by trauma type, age, sex, and reference data from contemporary literature. In our study group, burn scars constituted 55.8%, traumatic scars 13.3%, postoperative scars 20.8%, and inflammatory conditions 10%. Purulent-inflammatory diseases (e.g., furuncles, furunculosis) were categorized as inflammatory skin disorders. Among burn injuries, scalding with hot water or oil was most common.

The mean number of procedures performed per patient was 1.38 (range: 1–3). The mean energy per session was 4486.76 J (range: 388–17 536 J), and the mean power per session was 4 W (range: 3–6 W). The mean follow-up period was 7.2 months (range: 6–12 months).

Results. Postoperatively, scar thickness was evaluated at each visit. Doppler ultrasonography demonstrated a reduction of 0.308 ± 0.138 cm after 6 months ($p < 0.05$). Overall, scar thickness significantly decreased compared to baseline (from 0.633 ± 0.306 cm to 0.942 ± 0.377 cm). Scar thickness decreased by 27.7% in hypertrophic scars and by 28.2% in keloids.

Scar elasticity was also evaluated at each visit (rigidity parameters R0 and Q0 are inversely proportional to numerical elasticity indicators), demonstrating changes of 0.023 ± 0.008 ($p = 0.007$) and 2.616 ± 1.169 units ($p = 0.029$). Elasticity improved as follows: r0 from 1.82 ± 0.056 units to 1.9 ± 0.06 units, and g0 from 365.7 ± 13.113 units to 368.3 ± 12.5 units.

In both subgroups, improvement in the Vancouver Scar Scale was 1.2% for hypertrophic scars ($p < 0.05$) and 0.4% for keloids ($p = 0.26$), the latter not being statistically significant.

Regarding scar pigmentation, no significant improvement was observed in the combined subgroup. The melanin index decreased from 251.413 ± 157.716 units to 234.349 ± 90.708 units after 6 months, a difference of 17.063 ± 131.33 units ($p = 0.308$). However, in the keloid subgroup, pigmentation improved by 21.3% ($p < 0.01$).

Conclusion. This scientific study achieved satisfactory results confirming the effectiveness of the applied method in reducing the volume of scar tissue, improving its elasticity, and decreasing the severity of erythema, pigmentation, and vascular prominence within the scar. It should be emphasized that the penetration depth of laser irradiation is limited to 2–3 mm, which indicates the necessity of a combined therapeutic approach—both surgical intervention and laser therapy—for scars protruding more than 2 mm above the skin surface. In this regard, it is advisable to apply this laser technique in combination with other types of laser treatment or pharmacological agents.

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